

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

O'zbekiston
Milliy Pedagogika
Universiteti

№4(4)
2026

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

M

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Elektron nashr. 522 sahifa,
22-aprel, 2026-yil.

BOSH MUHARRIR:

Karimova E'zoza Gapijanovna – O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vaziri

BOSH MUHARRIR O'RINBOSARI:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor

TAHRIRIYAT KENGASHI A'ZOLARI

Ibragimov X.I. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, akademik
Shoumarov G'.B. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, akademik
Qirg'izboyev A.K. – Tarix fanlari doktori, professor
Jamoldinova O.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Sharipov Sh.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Ma'murov B.B. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Madraximova F.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Kalonov M.B. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Nabiyev D.X. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Qo'ldoshev Q. M. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Ikramxanova F.I. – filologiya fanlari doktori, professor
Ismagilova F.S. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Rossiya)
Stoyuxina N.Yu. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Rossiya)
Magauova A.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor (Qozog'iston)
Rejep O'zyurek – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Turkiya)
Wookyu Cha – Koreya milliy ta'lim universiteti rektori (Koreya)
Polonnikov A.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Belarus)
Mizayeva F. O. – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, dotsent
Baybayeva M.X. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Muxsiyeva A.T. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Aliyev B. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
Abdullayeva N. Sh. – Pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Doniyorov S. M. – “Yangi O'zbekiston” va “Pravda Vostoka” gazetalari tahririyati DM bosh muharriri, O'zbekiston Respublikasida xizmat ko'rsatgan jurnalist, filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
G'afurov D. O. – falsafa fanlari doktori (Phd)
Shomurodov R.T. – iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Mirzayeva F. O. – pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Jalilova S.X. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Bafayev M.M. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Usmonova D.I. – Samarqand iqtisodiyot va servis institute dotsenti
Saifnazarov I. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
Nematov Sh.E. – pedagogika fanlari nomzodi (PhD)
Tillashayxova X.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Yuldasheva F.I. – pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Yuldasheva D.B. – filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa (PhD) doktori, dotsent
Tangriyev A. T. – Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti kafedra professori
Ashurov R. R. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Panjiyev M. A. – Qashqadaryo viloyati Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi boshqarmasi boshlig'ining birinchi o'rinbosari
Xudayberganov N. A. – Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi Tabiiy fanlar bo'limining katta ilmiy xodimi, biologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Vaxobov Anvar Abdusattor o'g'li – Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent

Muassis: “Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon” MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vazirligi, O'zbekiston milliy pedagogika universiteti

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Karimova E'zoza Gapirzhanovna – Minister of Perschool and School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

EDITORIAL BOARD MEMBERS:

Ibragimov X.I. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Academician

Shoumarov G. B. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Academician

Qirg'izboyev A. K. – Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor

Jamoldinova O.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Sharipov Sh.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Ma'murov B.B. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Madraximova F.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Kalonov M.B. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Nabiyev D.X. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Koldoshev K. M. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Ikramxanova F.I. – Doctor of Philological Sciences, Professor

Ismagilova F.S. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Russia)

Stoyuxina N.Yu. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Russia)

Magauova A.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor (Kazakhstan)

Rejep O'zyurek – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Turkey)

Wookyu Cha – President of the National University of Education, Korea (South Korea)

Polonnikov A.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Belarus)

Mizayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Baybayeva M.X. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Muxsiyeva A.T. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Aliyev B. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Abdullayeva N. Sh. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Doniyorov S. M. – Editor-in-Chief of the DM Editorial Office of the newspapers “Yangi O'zbekiston” and “Pravda Vostoka”, Honored Journalist of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philology, Associate Professor

Gafurov D. O. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)

Shomurodov R.T. – Candidate of Economic Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Mirzayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

Jalilova S.X. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Bafayev M.M. – Doctor of Philosophy in Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Usmonova D.I. – Associate Professor, Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Saifnazarov I. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Nematov Sh.E. – Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences (PhD)

Tillashayxova X.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Yuldasheva F.I. – Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Yuldasheva D.B. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philological Sciences, Associate Professor

Tangriyev A.T. – is a professor of Tashkent State University of Economics

Ashurov R. R. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Psychology, Associate Professor

Panjiyev M. A. – First Deputy Head of the Department of Preschool and School Education of the Kashkadarya Region

Khudaiberganov N. A. – Senior Researcher of the Department of Natural Sciences of the Khorezm Mamun

Academy, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Biological Sciences

Vakhobov Anvar Abdusattor oglu – Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi” jurnali O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasining quyidagi qarorlariga asosan pedagogika va psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) hamda fan doktori (DSc) ilmiy darajasiga talabgorlarning dissertatsiyalaridagi asosiy ilmiy natijalarni chop etish uchun milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxatiga kiritilgan:

Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (08.05.2025-y., №370/5)

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan **№C-5669363**
reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha
ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

MUNDARIJA

Pedagog kadrlar tayyorlashda microteaching metodining tashkiliy asoslari va uni samarali qo'llash mexanizmlari.....	10
Abdiqayumova Malika	
Ijtimoiy pedagogik faoliyatning bolalarning moslashuv ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishdagi o'rni	14
Abdullayeva Yulduz Qurbon qizi, Xudayberdiyeva Zilola Azamat qizi	
Talabalarning og'zaki nutqini interfaol usullar yordamida rivojlantirish	18
Atamirzayeva Ezoza	
English Language Barriers Among Rural Ecotourism Guides in Uzbekistan	22
Aminova Asilaxon Sobir qizi	
Совершенствование методов обучения студентов эффективному управлению временем на основе тайм-менеджмента.....	25
Уразова М. Б., Абатова У. Б.	
Zamonaviy ta'limda innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalarning o'rni va samaradorligi	30
Xurramova Dilso'z Baxtiyor qizi	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida o'yin asosida ta'limni tashkil etishning pedagogik ahamiyati.....	33
Gaipova Akjunis Qayratovna	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda o'zini o'zi tashkil etish tushunchasi va uning pedagogik mohiyati.....	37
Alimov Bekzod Nematovich	
O'qituvchilarning uzluksiz kasbiy rivojlanish tadbirlarini maktab darajasida boshqarishning integratsiyalashgan yondashuvi	41
Ahadova Mushtariybonu Akmal qizi	
Talabalarning tanqidiy fikrlash ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishda innovatsion yondashuvlar	48
Xurramova Sanobar Mahmatmurod qizi	
Pedagogical Integration as a Factor of Humanization in Professional Teacher Education	53
Yusupova Mukhabbat Anatolyevna	
Yoshlarda iqtisodiy tafakkur shakllanishida etnik muhitning ta'siri.....	58
Erkinova Sevara Najmiddin qiz	
Innovative Approaches to Teaching English in Higher Education: a Methodological Study	61
Gulsara Khakimova	
Bo'lajak pedagoglarda kognitiv faollikni rivojlantirishda neyropedagogika asoslari.....	63
Hikmatova Jamila Fatox qizi	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi aqli zaif bolalarning eshituv idrokini rivojlantirish texnologiyalari.....	68
I. S. Xamrayeva, Nuriddinova Muxayyo Ishxodjayevna	
Badiiy matn asosida nutqiy ko'nikmalar va ijodiy tafakkur integratsiyasini ta'minlash metodikasi	73
Jo'rayeva Sevinch Abdialim qizi	
Etnopedagogik muhitda maktabgacha katta yoshdagi bolalarning nutqini rivojlantirish.....	77
Murodova Farangis G'anisherovna	
Malaka oshirish jarayonida muammoga asoslangan o'qitish vositasida MTT tarbiyachilarining 4K ko'nikmasini rivojlantirish texnologiyasi	81
Ravshanova Xafiza Komilovna	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida xalq og'zaki ijodi vositalaridan (ertak, maqol, qo'shiq, afsona, doston va boshqalar) foydalanishning nazariy asoslari, xalqaro va milliy tajribasi	85
Tog'ayeva Munisa Muxammadiyevna	
Akademik ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirish asosida kelajakdagi o'qituvchining kasbiy kompetensiyasini shakllantirish	89
Tursunova Elmira Ulug'bekovna, Rayimova Mushtariy Raup qizi	
Sensor integratsiya autizm spektri buzilishi bo'lgan bolalarning xulq-atvor va hissiy holatiga ta'siri.....	91
Xamidova Muyassar Polsaidovna, Abdullayeva Muslima Shovkat qizi	

Bo'lajak boshlang'ich ta'lim o'qituvchilarining mantiqiy fikrlashini rivojlantirishning pedagogik shart-sharoitlari	96
<i>Xoshimova Dilobar Kuchkarovna, Nortosheva Dildora Orif qizi, Avazmurodova Mehribon Sharif qizi</i>	
Инновационная методика нравственного воспитания в начальных классах: подход межпредметной интеграции	101
<i>Улугмурадова Шохсанам</i>	
Shaxs o'z-o'zini anglashining ijtimoiy-psixologik jihatlari	105
<i>Bobonazarov Oybek Shoyim o'g'li</i>	
Samarqand arxitektura-qurilish instituti va shahar infratuzilmasi rivojlanishi o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik (1950–1990yy).....	108
<i>Abulqosimova Dildora Asrorovna, O'ralov Sodiqjon</i>	
Tabiatshunoslik darslarida steam yondashuvi asosida ta'limni tashkil etish metodlari	111
<i>Gulnora Narmatova Tojiyevna</i>	
AI-Mediated Coil in Oral English Teacher Education: a Didactic Model for Developing Intercultural Communicative Competence.....	115
<i>Mukhammadiyeva Khalima Saidakhmadovna</i>	
Pedagogik faoliyatda kasbiy stress jarayonining ijtimoiy psixologik xususiyatlari	119
<i>Xotamova Madinabonu Iloxmon qizi</i>	
Pedagogik mahorat fani asosida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning refleksiv ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish texnologiyalari.....	123
<i>Xurramova Mohidil Baxtiyorovna</i>	
Bo'lajak kutubxonachilarda ilm-fanga oid bilimlarni o'zlashtirish malakasini shakllantirish	126
<i>O'rozov Abdurasul Norboyevich</i>	
Методологические подходы к развитию духовно-творческого потенциала детей младшего школьного возраста	130
<i>Хасанова Гулшод Касимовна</i>	
Pedagogik ta'lim transformatsiyasida talabalarning tadqiqotchilik kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish texnologiyasi.....	134
<i>Rustamova Shoxista Omonjonovna</i>	
O'rta maktab yoshidagi o'quvchilarda voleybol mashg'ulotlarining psixoemotsional holat va ijtimoiy faollikka ta'siri	138
<i>Xonimqulova Durdona</i>	
Farzandlar tarbiyasida otalik va onalik hissining shakllanishining o'ziga xosligi	141
<i>Tursunboyeva Gavharoy Abdivohid qizi</i>	
O'quv jarayonida raqamli kontent (elektron darslik, multimedia materiallari) yaratish texnologiyalari.....	145
<i>Quvatov Shuxrat Akmurodovich, Rashidov Anvarjon Sharipovich</i>	
Scratch dasturida harflarni vizuallashtirish orqali 1-sinf o'quvchilarining tasavvurlarini rivojlantirish usullarini takomillashtirish.....	150
<i>Normurodova Sadoqat Xoliqulovna</i>	
Vaqtini boshqarish hamda to'g'ri taqsimlashning pedagog hayoti va faoliyatidagi ahamiyati.....	155
<i>Tursunova Nilufar</i>	
Sun'iy intellektning ingliz tili o'qitishdagi roli	159
<i>Burxonova Aziza Ikhtiyorovna, Negova Feruza Sharifovna</i>	
Разработка системы адаптивной генерации контрольных вопросов из учебных материалов на узбекском языке на основе гибридного подхода ИИ и таксономии Блума	162
<i>Бегалиев Жалолiddин Камолiddинович, Маматов Ислombек Ильесович</i>	
Применение данных беспилотной авиации для обновления картографических данных	168
<i>Хакимов Дониёр Бахтиёр угли, Бурунова Муниса Баходировна</i>	
The Role and Significance of the Acmeological Approach in the Managerial Activity of School Principals.....	172
<i>Normurodova Aziza Zuxriddin qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak pedagoglarda tarbiya darslarini samarali tashkil etishga o'rgatish: mazmuni, shakli va metodlari ..	178
<i>Sheraliyeva Nasiba Alimkulovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda ijtimoiy xulq-atvorni shakllantirishda ota-ona tarbiya uslublarining pedagogik imkoniyatlari.....	184
<i>Ashurova Aziza Erkinovna</i>	

Mintaqaviy sanoat korxonalarining biznes jarayonlarini tahlil qilish va baholashning zamonaviy usullari (BPM, Lean, Six Sigma yondashuvlari misolida)	188
<i>Azimova Maxfuza Rashidovna</i>	
O'zbekistonda turli etnik guruhlarda mehnat motivatsiyasining qiyosiy tahlili.....	193
<i>Erkinova Sevara Najmiddin qizi, Saidakbarova E'zozaxon Muzaffar qizi</i>	
"Geogebra" dasturi yordamida geometriya va matematik analiz kursini o'qitishda vizual tafakkurni rivojlantirish metodikasi.....	196
<i>Fayzullayeva E'zoza O'tkir qizi</i>	
Umumta'lim maktablarida raqamli transformatsiya texnologiyalarini qo'llashning zarurati.....	200
<i>Musurmanova Shodiya Xolmuratovna</i>	
Raqamli ta'lim texnologiyalari va sun'iy intellekt asosida ta'lim jarayonini takomillashtirish.....	204
<i>O'ktamov Madadjon O'ktam o'g'li, Boymurodova Shahzoda Alisher qizi</i>	
Gimnastikada akrobatik mashqlarni rivojlantirish metodikasi	208
<i>Raxmatova Nodira Muxtorjon qizi</i>	
Suggestiv metodlar asosida xulqi og'ishgan bolalar uchun tarbiyaviy mashg'ulotlarni loyihalash	212
<i>Shermatova Manzura Ikromjanovna</i>	
Tabaqalashtirilgan yondashuv asosida tayyorlov guruh tarbiyalanuvchilarini maktab ta'limiga tayyorlash ...	216
<i>Sanayeva S. B., Toshqulova Z. U.</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarida ekologik tafakkurni rivojlantirishning dolzarbligi.....	220
<i>Yaxshiboyeva Nargiza Rustamqulovna</i>	
Понятие искусственного интеллекта в контексте образования и его педагогические функции	224
<i>Каримова Сабина Собировна</i>	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarda kasbiy barqarorlik ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishning pedagogik-psixologik omillari....	230
<i>Akramjonova Feruza Akramjonovna</i>	
Demografik yuklama sharoitida maktab pedagogik jamoasini samarali boshqarishning hr-strategiyalari.....	233
<i>Axmadqulova Ozodaxon Hamidullo qizi</i>	
Kasbiy identifikatsiya – shaxsning kasbiy o'zligini shakllantirish omili sifatida	236
<i>Bazarov Xayotbek Ne'matovich</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida qoraqalpoq xalq ertaklari asosida multimediyali mahsulotlar yaratish samaradorligi.....	240
<i>Bekimbetova Aynagul Amangeldievna, Ollaberganova Mohira</i>	
Odam anatomiyasi va fiziologiyasi darslarida muammoli ta'lim texnologiyalari orqali talabalarning ijodiy izlanuvchanligini faollashtirish.....	245
<i>Haydarova Pardaxol Boboqulovna</i>	
Chet el va O'zbekiston tajribasida ota-onalar bilan hamkorlikni tashkil etishning metodologiyasi	249
<i>Inomova Madina</i>	
Boshlag'ich ta'lim tabiiy fanlarini o'qitishda o'quvchilarning ijodkorligini shakllantirish metodikasi.....	253
<i>Ismatova Zulayho Asadovna, Avazova Gulnoza Qodirjon qizi</i>	
Innovatsion ta'lim muhitida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida ekologik tarbiyani shakllantirishning samarali yo'llari	256
<i>Ismatova Zulayho Asadovna, Xamroyeva Ozoda Norbo'ta qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'qish savodxonligi darslarida o'quvchilarning so'z boyligi va nutqiy ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish	259
<i>Mambetova Lobar Mirzavali qizi, Rajabova Nafisaxon Dilmurod qizi</i>	
Kasbiy faoliyatda pedagogik improvizatsiya ijodiy kompetensiya sifatida	264
<i>Miraxmedova Dilafro'zxon Nurilloxon qizi, Jo'rayeva Gulshodaxon Ibrohimjon qizi</i>	
Media savodxonlik tushunchasi va uning pedagogik ta'limdagi ahamiyati.....	267
<i>Salomova Lobar Sobir qizi</i>	
Innovatsion ta'lim muhitida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida estetik tarbiyani shakllantirish metodikasi	271
<i>Tursunova Malika Baxtiyor qizi, Aminova Oltinay Davranbek qizi</i>	
STEAM texnologiyasi asosida o'quvchilarning ijodiy tafakkurini rivojlantirish metodikasi	274
<i>Xaydarova Dilafuz Abdukurim qizi</i>	

Refleksiv ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirish – bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni kasbiy faoliyatga tayyorlash bosqichi sifatida.....	279
<i>Jo'rayeva Maftuna Dilshodbek qizi</i>	
Chimyon–Chorvoq kurort-rekreatsiya zonasidagi rekreatsiya obyektlari va ulardan foydalanish holati	283
<i>Djurayeva Lobar Vaxitovna</i>	
G'ovlar osha yuguruvchi qizlarning maxsus jismoniy tayyorgarlik darajasini oshirish asosida sport musobaqalariga tayyorlash.....	286
<i>Sattorqulova Fotima Jamol qizi, Sattorqulova Zuhra Jamol qizi</i>	
Grammatika va yozuv ko'nikmasining integratsiyalashuvini ESL o'quvchilarning grammatik ravonligini o'stirishdagi ahamiyati	292
<i>Ne'matova Iroda Ilhom qizi, Karimova Xadicha Fazliddin qizi</i>	
Формирование экологической культуры и проектных компетенций молодежи в формате хакатона “Климатон–25”	295
<i>Бегмуратова Зоя Асаматдиновна</i>	
Portlovchi kuch sifatini rivojlantirishning nazariy va metodik asoslari.....	298
<i>Xushvaqtov Shaxzod Mamatqul o'g'li</i>	
Enhancing the Writing Skills of Non-Philological Students Through Artificial Intelligence Tools	302
<i>Rajabova Rakhimakhon Maksudovna</i>	
Supporting Children With Autism in Inclusive Education: Effectiveness of Multisensory, Visual Scheduling, and ABA Approaches.....	306
<i>Safarova Sanobar Omontashevna, Rakhimova Ozoda Abdurasul qizi</i>	
O'quv topshiriqlari orqali 6-sinf o'quvchilarining pragmatik kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishdagi leksik birliklar bilan ishlashning ahamiyati	310
<i>Ashirbayeva Nafisa Aminbayevna</i>	
O'smirlarda nevrotik holatlarning namoyon bo'lish xususiyatlari va ularni diagnostika qilishning nazariy-metodologik asoslari	313
<i>Abduraximov Doniyor Abdusaid o'g'li</i>	
Ingliz tilini o'rgatishda talabalarning ijodiy fikrlashini rivojlantirish metodlari.....	317
<i>Abirqulova Nafisa Abdusalamovna</i>	
Yuqori sinf ingliz tili darslarida tanqidiy fikrlashni rivojlantirishning innovatsion metodik modeli	321
<i>Ahmadjonova Diyoraxon Dilshod qizi</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlarini innovatsion yondashuvlar asosida tashkil etish va pedagogik muloqot madaniyati	326
<i>Alimov Shavkatbek Shuxratbekovich</i>	
Identification and Systematization of Emotional Intelligence Indicators in Pre-Service Primary School Teachers.....	330
<i>Aminova Nasiba Davlatboy kizi</i>	
Oligofren bolalarda kognitiv jarayonlarni rivojlantirishda o'yin terapiyasining nazariy-metodologik asoslari va pedagogik samaradorligi	334
<i>Amirsaidova Sh. M., Jumanazarova Mashhura San'atbek qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf ona tili va o'qish savodxonligi darslarida matn ustida ishlash metodikasi	339
<i>Asilbekova Shoxsanam To'liqin qizi</i>	
O'zbekistonda olimpiya harakatini rivojlantirishning pedagogik asoslari	344
<i>Axmadiyeva Gulnoz Ikramovna</i>	
Zamonaviy tibbiyotda hissiyotlarni boshqarishning ijtimoiy-psixologik xususiyatlari.....	348
<i>Azgarova Gulsum Alisher qizi</i>	
The Use of Problem-Based Learning Methods in Delivering High-Quality Education in Schools	351
<i>Bekmuratova U'mit Ken'esbay qizi, Abdiev Azamat</i>	
Akseleratsiyaning o'quvchilar xulq-atvoriga ta'siri	355
<i>Botirova Oydina Vadimovna</i>	
Ta'limda zamonaviy pedagogik innovatsiyalar va raqamli transformatsiya: bo'lajak ingliz tili o'qituvchilarni tayyorlashning metodologik asoslari	361
<i>Eshimova Nasiba Zohiddin qizi</i>	

Kasbiy samaradorlikni oshirishda sun'iy intellektning roli: "KasbNavigator" platformasi misolida	365
<i>Isayeva Oylarxon Ro'zimatjon qizi, Sobirov Muslimjon Muxsinjon o'g'li</i>	
Ixtisoslashtirilgan maktablarda o'quvchilarning nutqiy faoliyatini rivojlantirish: integratsiyalashgan ta'lim va ijodiy yondashuv.....	369
<i>Mavlanova Saidaxon Umarovna</i>	
Yoshlar orasida ijtimoiy tarmoqlardan foydalanishning depressiv holatlarga ta'siri	373
<i>Mirzaxmatova Sayyora Saydaxmatovna</i>	
Kiberijtimoiylashuv sharoitida avlodlararo kommunikativ o'zaro ta'sirning psixologik xususiyatlari.....	375
<i>Muhiddinova Mamlakat Nabi qizi</i>	
"Emotional Learning Analytics"metodi asosida o'qituvchilarning refleksiv kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish ...	380
<i>Omonqulova Diyora Farhod qizi</i>	
Talabalarda milliy identiklikni shakllantirishning nazariy asoslari.....	384
<i>Qudratov Davron Sami o'g'li</i>	
Media kompetentlik va media savodxonlik tushunchalarining ilmiy-pedagogik mohiyati, tarkibi va rivojlanish tarixi.....	388
<i>Rahimova Xosiyat Uralovna</i>	
Yangilanayotgan O'zbekistonda tarix fani oqituvchilarining kasbiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishning nazariy va metodik asoslari	392
<i>Raxmatova Ondagul Oybek qizi</i>	
Talabalarining kasbiy tayyorgarligida mantiqiy fikrlashini rivojlantirish kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishning pedagogik muamolari.....	395
<i>Raxmonova Mavluda Suvon qizi</i>	
O'smirlarni kiberbulling tahdididan himoya qilishning psixologik mexanizmlari	398
<i>Sattorova Mohinur Sherali qizi</i>	
Bolalarda oilaga hurmat va qadriyatli munosabatni rivojlantirish jarayonida ota-ona bilan hamkorlik qilish yo'llari	401
<i>Sharofutdinova Nigora Kenja qizi, Usarova Marg'uba Nazar qizi</i>	
O'zbekistonda o'qituvchilar malakasini oshirishning vertikal modeli: tizimli tahlil va cheklovlar	405
<i>Toxirova Nafisa Dilshod qizi</i>	
Fizika fanini o'qitishda maxsus ehtiyojli o'quvchilar uchun texnologiyalar va tajribalarning roli	409
<i>Tursunov Alisher Isoqovich, G'ulomov Davlatbek Istat o'g'li</i>	
MTTda qadriyatlar kompetentligini rivojlantirish vositalari	412
<i>Urinova Rushana Tursunniyozovna, Usarova Marg'uba Nazar qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda nutq o'stirish metodikasini takomillashtirish.....	415
<i>Xakimova Xosiyat Jurayevna</i>	
O'smirlik davrida deviant xulq-atvor namoyon bo'lishining psixologik xususiyatlari	419
<i>Xalilova Sarvinoz Qodirali qizi</i>	
Ta'lim platformalarida mustaqil ta'lim ma'lumotlarini relyatsion model asosida optimallashtirish	422
<i>Xasanov Baxrom Boktiboyevich</i>	
Применение информационных технологий для интеллектуального анализа чрезвычайных ситуаций на основе edge computing и компьютерного зрения.....	426
<i>Мамаражабов Музаффар Абдурасулович, Маматов Ислонбек Ильесович</i>	
Индивидуальное интеллектуальное развитие личности – как педагогическая проблема	432
<i>Олтибоева Камола Шарофжон кизи</i>	
Представления о реальной и виртуальной дружбе у подростков	436
<i>Хамидова Нигора Илхомовна</i>	
5–7-сinf o'quvchilarining mustaqil ijodiy faoliyatini rivojlantirishda milliy hunarmandchilik an'analaridan foydalanish metodikasi.....	440
<i>Mahmudova Shaxnoza Mansur qizi, Amrullayeva Oisha Azamat qizi</i>	
Raqamli transformatsiya sharoitida olimpiya ta'limini rivojlantirishning innovatsion mexanizmlari.....	445
<i>Qodirov Jurabek Mamatsimonovich</i>	

Fizika ta'limida energiya va impuls saqlanish qonunlarini raqamli texnologiyalar (PhET, Crocodile Physics va h.k.) dan foydalanib o'qitish imkoniyatlari.....	449
<i>Bozorov Hasan Ne'matovich, Ismatova Marjona Murod qizi</i>	
PIRLS tadqiqotlari asosida maktab direktorlarining boshqaruv kompetensiyalarini baholash va monitoring qilish tizimini takomillashtirish.....	455
<i>Badalova Maqsuda Umarovna, Oltiyeva Bibisora Ziyodullayevna</i>	
Rus tili darslarida o'qitish metodikasi.....	459
<i>Aminova Munisa G'ayrat qizi</i>	
Ingliz va o'zbek tillarida milliy o'zlikni ifodalovchi idiomalarning qiyosiy tadqiqi.....	462
<i>Nodira Sabirova, Bahar Kakyshova</i>	
Turizmni rivojlantirishdagi asosiy muammolar va imkoniyatlar	467
<i>Azimova Matlubaxon Abduraxmanovna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'limda ekologik madaniyatni shakllantirish: yashil bog'cha tajribasi	472
<i>Xakimov Abbasxon Oribjon o'g'li, Axmadjonova Nozanin Nizom qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti va otm hamkorligi, nazariya va amaliyot uyg'unligi.....	475
<i>Buranova Shoxnoza Abdurazakovna</i>	
Zamonaviy sport inshootlarida elektr energiyaning o'rni va undan samarali foydalanish.....	479
<i>Azatov Inomjon Axmed o'g'li</i>	
Aqli zaif bolalarda ijtimoiy moslashuvni rivojlantirishning pedagogik asoslari	482
<i>Amirsaidova Sh. M., Ro'ziqulova Shahrizoda Shuhrat qizi</i>	
Talabalarda tolerantlik sifatlarini rivojlantirishda vitogen ta'lim texnologiyasining amaliy jihatlari.....	486
<i>Dilmurotova Vazira Umidjon qizi</i>	
Ta'lim menejmentida jamoatchilik bilan muloqot tushunchasi va uning boshqaruv tizimidagi o'rni	489
<i>Islamova Dilfuza Dilshodovna</i>	
The Relationship Between Conscientiousness and Writing Skills of Secondary School Pupils.....	495
<i>Ne'matova Umida Jumanazar qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich tayyorgarlik guruhidagi karatechilarning mashg'ulot jarayonini takomillashtirish	498
<i>Raxmonov Boburbek Oybekovich</i>	
Imkoniyati cheklangan o'quvchilarga fizika fanini o'qitishning hozirgi holati va tahlili.....	502
<i>Tursunov Alisher Isoqovich, G'ulomov Davlatbek Istat o'g'li</i>	
Sun'iy intellekt va innovatsion texnologiyalar kasbiy stressni keltiruvchi omili sifatida	505
<i>Vaxobova Durdona To'lanboy qizi</i>	
Moslashuvchan jinsiylik va hayotiy ko'nikmalar ta'limi (ASLSE) modelining nazariy asoslari	508
<i>Xamidova Muyassar Polsaidovna, Salimov Muhriddin Faxriddin o'g'li</i>	
Sun'iy intellekt va lotin tilini o'qitish o'rtasidagi o'zaro bog'liqlik.....	512
<i>Yuldasheva Dilshoda Yuldashevna</i>	
Роман П. Кадырова “Олмос камар” как национальная гордость узбекского народа	515
<i>Джалматова Замира Джоникуловна</i>	

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CONSCIENTIOUSNESS AND WRITING SKILLS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL PUPILS

Ne'matova Umida Jumanazar qizi

Shahrisabz davlat pedagogika instituti

“Xorijiy til va adabiyoti” yo'nalishi magistratura talabasi

ORCID: 0009-0007-6960-5672

Abstract: This study aims to explore the relationship between writing skills and personality traits, with a particular focus on conscientiousness and its association with writing development. The research examines Grade 7 secondary school EFL learners and investigates how levels of conscientiousness relate to their writing performance. The study assesses students' written work using a structured scoring rubric and analyzes the data with reference to both the level of conscientiousness and the development of writing skills. The scientific novelty of this research lies in its focus on the relationship between conscientiousness and writing skills among secondary school EFL learners, a context that has received limited attention in previous studies.

Key words: conscientiousness, writing skills, personality, academic performance, EFL learners.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot yozish ko'nikmalari va shaxsiy xususiyatlar o'rtasidagi munosabatni o'rganishga qaratilgan bo'lib, ayniqsa vijdonlilik (conscientiousness) va uning yozish ko'nikmalari bilan bog'liqligiga alohida e'tibor qaratadi. Tadqiqot 7-sinf o'rta maktab ingliz tilini chet tili sifatida o'rganuvchi (EFL) o'quvchilarini qamrab oladi hamda vijdonlilik darajasi ularning yozish ko'rsatkichlari bilan qanday bog'liqligini tahlil qiladi. Tadqiqotda o'quvchilarning yozma ishlari maxsus ishlab chiqilgan baholash mezonini (scoring rubric) asosida baholanadi va ma'lumotlar vijdonlilik darajasi hamda yozish ko'nikmalarining rivojlanishi nuqtayi nazaridan tahlil qilinadi. Mazkur tadqiqotning ilmiy yangiligi shundaki, u o'rta maktab EFL o'quvchilari orasida vijdonlilik va yozish ko'nikmalari o'rtasidagi munosabatni o'rganishga qaratilgan bo'lib, bu yo'nalish avvalgi tadqiqotlarda yetarlicha yoritilmagan.

Kalit so'zlar: vijdonlilik, yozish, shaxsiyat, akademik natijalar, EFL o'quvchilari.

Аннотация: Данное исследование направлено на изучение взаимосвязи между навыками письма и личностными чертами, с особым акцентом на добросовестность (conscientiousness) и её связь с развитием письменной речи. В исследовании рассматриваются учащиеся 7-х классов средних школ, изучающие английский язык как иностранный (EFL), и анализируется, как уровень добросовестности связан с их письменными результатами. В рамках исследования письменные работы учащихся оцениваются с использованием структурированной шкалы оценивания (scoring rubric), а полученные данные анализируются с учётом уровня добросовестности и развития письменных навыков. Научная новизна данного исследования заключается в изучении взаимосвязи между добросовестностью и навыками письма у учащихся средней школы, изучающих английский язык как иностранный, что ранее было недостаточно освещено в научной литературе.

Ключевые слова: добросовестность, навыки письма, личностные черты, академическая успеваемость, учащиеся EFL.

INTRODUCTION

Learners need to develop strong writing skills for effective communication and academic success. Being a proficient writer also fosters critical thinking, enabling individuals to organize complex ideas and express them clearly. Writing is often considered one of the most challenging skills to acquire, as it involves multiple stages in producing a coherent final product. Effective writing requires the ability to organize ideas logically and connect them smoothly to create a cohesive text. However, many learners struggle with various aspects of writing, including idea generation, organization, appropriate word order in the target language, and accurate vocabulary usage. The importance of strong writing skills is particularly evident in contexts such as résumés, emails, and academic essays, where first impressions matter. Writing also allows individuals to express their thoughts in a structured way and can contribute to emotional regulation. Regular writing practice has been shown to reduce anxiety and promote a sense of relief for the writer.

Learning is closely connected to human psychology; therefore, personality traits can significantly influence learning processes and outcomes. Personality affects how individuals plan, draft, and revise their writing, as well as how they develop their writing style and voice. For instance, individuals with more expressive personalities may use more emotional language, whereas others may adopt a more direct and concise style to convey their ideas and opinions. Perfectionists may struggle with drafting, while others may rely on creative, unstructured bursts of writing. Personality is connected to writing through both the physical act of handwriting and the creative writing process. Historically, trait-based personality assessment has been used to predict academic performance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Several meta-analyses have examined the relationship between personality and academic performance. The Big Five personality traits (also called the Five-Factor Model) is one of the most widely used frameworks in psychology for describing human personality. Andrew Poropat stated that this model includes the dimensions of Agreeableness (likeability and friendliness), Conscientiousness (dependability and achievement orientation), Emotional Stability (adjustment versus anxiety), Extraversion (activity and sociability), and Openness (imagination and intellectual curiosity). He found that Conscientiousness is the strongest predictor of academic performance and has a significant influence on writing performance ^[1].

Conscientiousness involves organization and accuracy. Therefore, learners with high conscientiousness tend to write more neatly and clearly, plan structural components such as the introduction, body, and conclusion before writing, and make fewer grammatical and spelling errors. In contrast, learners with low conscientiousness are often characterized by disorganized ideas, weak structure, and frequent errors. This trait strongly influences how well-structured and accurate writing is. High conscientiousness also promotes better organization and planning.

Poropat also found that academic performance correlates significantly with Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, and Openness to Experience. He noted that correlations between Conscientiousness and academic performance are largely independent of intelligence. Additionally, conscientiousness tends to be more pronounced in tertiary education learners. Christopher Farsides and Richard Woodfield suggested that age may moderate the relationship between personality and academic performance, although this was not directly tested ^[2].

Aivi Laidra, Helle Pullmann, and Jüri Allik found that increasing age is associated with reduced correlations between academic performance and intelligence, while also moderating other relationships ^[3].

Furthermore, studies by Mikael Mac Giolla and Petri Kajonius, as well as Nguyen et al., indicate that women tend to score higher in conscientiousness than men, which may partly explain gender differences in academic achievement ^{[4][5]}.

Oliver John and Sanjay Srivastava describe conscientiousness as involving responsibility, organization, diligence, and self-discipline ^[6]. Multiple studies have confirmed that conscientiousness is one of the strongest and most consistent predictors of academic achievement, particularly in postsecondary education.

Brian O'Connor and Sampo Paunonen, along with Poropat and Trapmann et al., emphasize its predictive power. Poropat further argued that conscientiousness can predict academic achievement at a level comparable to intelligence and may even operate independently of it. Komarraju et al. found that effective learning strategies also contribute to academic success ^{[7][8]}. Despite extensive research on personality and academic performance, gaps remain—particularly regarding the influence of personality traits on specific language skills such as writing. Therefore, this study addresses this gap by focusing on the relationship between conscientiousness and writing development.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative data analysis approach and utilizes the Big Five Inventory (BFI) personality test to explore the relationship between conscientiousness, writing skills, and academic success. Participants were selected from Grade 7 secondary school pupils and were assigned multiple writing tasks involving short paragraphs on familiar topics. Data were collected using two primary instruments. First, the Big Five Inventory (BFI) was administered to measure students' levels of conscientiousness. Second, a set of writing tasks was designed, requiring participants to produce short paragraphs on familiar topics. Students' written responses were evaluated using a structured scoring rubric focusing on grammar, vocabulary, coherence, and organization.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The data were analyzed using a structured scoring rubric to assess the students' written paragraphs. The participants consisted of 14 pupils whose levels of conscientiousness were measured using the Big Five Inventory (BFI). The findings indicate that pupils with higher levels of conscientiousness demonstrated better perfor-

mance in writing tasks. Among the participants, five students identified as highly conscientious showed strong writing ability, particularly in terms of organization and grammatical accuracy. Their written work was generally well structured and coherent. Five students with moderate levels of conscientiousness displayed some difficulties in writing. Their performance revealed issues in organization, grammatical accuracy, and vocabulary usage, although they were able to complete the tasks at an acceptable level.

In contrast, four students with low levels of conscientiousness showed weaker performance across the assessed criteria. These pupils made frequent grammatical and structural errors and demonstrated limited attention to writing conventions and task requirements. Overall, the results suggest a clear pattern in which higher levels of conscientiousness are associated with better writing performance among the participants. The findings of this study indicate that higher levels of conscientiousness are associated with better writing performance among Grade 7 pupils. The results suggest that conscientiousness does not directly cause improved writing performance; rather, it is positively associated with writing skills. Writing is a complex activity involving multiple simultaneous processes, including organization, vocabulary selection, grammatical accuracy, and coherence. Therefore, not all learners achieve the same level of academic success in writing.

The findings further suggest that writing performance is closely related to individual differences, particularly personality traits such as conscientiousness. Students with higher levels of conscientiousness tend to demonstrate greater attention to detail and better organization, which may contribute to more effective writing. These results are consistent with previous research indicating that conscientiousness is positively associated with academic performance. This relationship may be explained by the cognitive demands of writing, which require planning, organization, and sustained attention. Students with higher levels of conscientiousness are more likely to manage these processes effectively. However, this study has several limitations, including a small sample size and the use of descriptive analysis, which may restrict the generalizability of the findings. Despite these limitations, the study highlights the importance of considering personality traits in the development of students' writing skills. It suggests that fostering students' organizational skills and sense of responsibility may contribute to improved writing performance.

CONCLUSION

Writing skill development is as important as other language skills for English learners and requires considerable effort to master. Moreover, it is closely related to learners' behavioral characteristics, which is why many researchers have examined the relationship between writing development and personality traits. In this study, one such trait – conscientiousness – was explored in relation to writing development and its association with academic performance. The data were collected through writing samples obtained from secondary school pupils and assessed using a structured rubric.

The findings suggest that higher levels of conscientiousness are associated with better writing performance. Learners with higher conscientiousness demonstrated stronger abilities in planning, revising, and producing more accurate and well-organized written work. However, these findings cannot be generalized to all educational contexts, as the study was conducted on a small sample of pupils and included a limited range of writing tasks. For future research, it is recommended that, in addition to descriptive analysis, correlation analysis be conducted to further examine the relationship between conscientiousness and writing performance.

Reference:

1. Poropat A.E. (2009). A meta-analysis of the five-factor model of personality and academic performance. *Psychological Bulletin*, 135(2), 322–338.
2. Farsides T., Woodfield R. (2003). Individual differences and undergraduate academic success: The roles of personality, intelligence, and application. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 33, 1225–1243.
3. Laidra K., Pullman H., Allik J. (2007). Personality and intelligence as predictors of academic achievement: A cross-sectional study from elementary to secondary school.
4. Mac Giolla E.M., Kajonius P.J. (2018). Sex differences in personality are larger in gender-equal countries: Replicating and extending a surprising finding. *International Journal of Psychology*, 54(6), 705–711.
5. Nguyen N.T., Allen L.C., Fraccastoro K. (2005). Personality predicts academic performance: Exploring the moderating role of gender. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 27(1), 105–117.
6. John O.P., Srivastava S. (1999). The Big Five trait taxonomy: History, measurement and theoretical perspectives. In L.A. Pervin & O.P. John (Eds.), *Handbook of personality: Theory and research* (pp. 102–138). Guilford.
7. O'Connor M.C., Pautonen S.V. (2007). Big Five personality predictors of post-secondary academic performance. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 43(5), 971–990.
8. Komaraju M., Karau S.J., Schmeck R.R., Avdic A. (2011). The Big Five personality traits, learning styles, and academic achievement. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 51(4), 472–477.

-
- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2026. №4(4)

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.